

SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO DIDACTIC TASKS DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *It is very important to develop listening comprehension skills in elementary school students. For this reason, the issue of using didactic games and systematic approach to didactic tasks in the development of listening comprehension in primary school students occupied the central part of the article.*

Keywords: *mother tongue and reading literacy, listening comprehension, systematic approach, linguistic competence, speaking activity.*

In modern society, studying every subject in general education schools, applying different approaches within subjects is one of the requirements of today's modern education. For this reason, it is important to pay attention to the development of students' linguistic competence in primary school students, especially in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, and to implement a systematic approach to achieve efficiency in this regard.

Form and content are perceived as a whole when listening to speech in the native language. As a result of the formation of lexical, grammatical and pronunciation skills, competence in this type of speech activity is formed. Understanding is easier if the language units used by the listener and the speaker match. This, in turn, is a matter of language experience. Listening comprehension is a three-stage activity, the content of the speech is perceived, learned and understood behind the general auditory perception (acoustic apperception), distinguishing the sound side of words (phonemics) and understanding the essence. Perhaps it is more clearly demonstrated in this process that listening comprehension, which is considered a type of speech activity and a skill, is the goal and means of education.

For the successful implementation of listening comprehension, the following three factors are considered:

- * dependence on the listener (development of hearing skills, memory, attention characteristics);
- * listening conditions (speed of speech, volume and form of language material, and how long the spoken speech lasts);
- * Linguistic aspects of the used material are taken into account. According to the second approach used by teachers, listening comprehension is directly related to the formation of speaking skills. In the process of teaching speaking, reading and writing, students engage in listening comprehension.

So how do these factors relate to the elementary school, to students in elementary education, or to elementary school mother tongue and reading literacy classes? the question arises. In order to answer this question in a broader context, it was considered necessary to give the following opinions.

It is well known that listening is the ability to distinguish and understand what others are saying, and in relation to the educational work in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, it is the auditory understanding of speech in the mother tongue in passing. This includes understanding the speaker's accent, grammatical structures, and the speaker's vocabulary.

The content of teaching listening comprehension in the primary grade refers to what and what to teach about listening comprehension. In this regard, G. V. Rogova divides the content into 3 parts, which are as follows:

1. Linguistic part - this includes language and speech material.
2. The psychological part is the ability to listen and understand speech.
3. Methodical part. It is determined to teach the students the ways of listening and understanding, and through the technology of listening and understanding, it is taught through rules, principles, methods, and tools.

Although the terms exercise and assignment are often found in textbooks and manuals, they are not synonymous. However, based on our observations, we can say that in a number of textbooks and manuals that have been in use for many years, there are cases where these two concepts are confused, one is used instead of the other. Taking these reasons as a problem, paying close attention to the methodology of developing linguistic competences of elementary school students by means of didactic games served to express the relevance of scientific research.

It can be thought as follows: an exercise is a means of developing skills in mastering a given new topic, and an assignment is a means of teaching a student to work independently, to think, to search. And didactic games become an "assistant force" that greatly helps in the development of linguistic competence of students. That is, after the student acquires skills in learning a new topic based on exercises and assignments, acquires the competence to work independently, think, and search, he can do all this while completing educational tasks based on didactic games. applies in practice. Because as soon as he hears the concept of a didactic game, he begins to look at the situation not as a forced situation, but as a fun game event, and with this, the student moves freely in completing the tasks of the didactic game.

Thus, in the development of listening comprehension skills with the help of didactic games, first of all, the speech should be broadcast for different purposes and the tasks of the didactic game should be different. Today, you can find many guides that are designed to build and develop listening comprehension skills. Almost all of them, of course, are enriched with audio resources that help practice listening comprehension skills. Effective and appropriate use of these in the lesson processes organized in the primary language and reading literacy ensures speed and convenience in reaching the intended goal.

To develop students' listening comprehension skills in the subject of mother tongue and reading literacy and to apply didactic game tasks, first of all, to be able to interest them in the lesson with the help of various didactic games, and then to interact with them in various ways is to provide conditions for independent expression of opinion using methods. It is also possible to increase the potential of students by ensuring the introduction of didactic games in order to convey the resources of the textbook to students in various non-traditional ways.

The connection of the audio text content with the previously learned lexical-grammatical material, the speed of hearing the speech, the orientation of the organized exercises to the development of students' auditory memory, the audio text content comprehensively affects all the

students' senses through audio-visual means It is also important to state. It is a priority to incorporate all of Bullring's didactic game tasks into native language and reading literacy classes.

Popular media (movies, music, YouTube) is a familiar tool for every person learning a language, and we are well aware that even elementary school students are not ignorant of these tools today. These tools help to attract attention and keep students interested in the theories and concepts being discussed. Because they can see theory and concepts in practice. Theory and concepts literally jump off the screen. Students can improve their analytical skills by analyzing media using the theories and concepts they are studying. Developing and implementing didactic game tasks based on the use of mass media in the classroom allows students to see concepts and new examples while watching TV, listening to music, or going to the movies with friends. In conclusion, it can be concluded that in order to teach students to make effective sentences, it is necessary to work regularly, continuously, from the primary grade, especially in the mother tongue and reading literacy classes, to include these types of exercises in didactic game tasks. it can be said that the organization serves to ensure the effectiveness of the speech of elementary school students. It should also be noted that the problem of teaching students to perceive the original speech by ear from elementary school is one of the most important aspects of teaching language communication, therefore, the development and development of listening teaching technologies that meet the needs of the times, it is extremely important to turn them into didactic games or didactic game-assignments suitable for students of primary school age, and to actively use them in the teaching process.

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